

Scope, Challenges and Emerging Trends of Corporate Finance in India

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the scope, challenges and trends in corporate finance in India. Developing countries like India need industries to grow their economy. It supports farming, protects the country, and helps the country grow evenly. Finance is one of the major tools that are required to setup an industry. It is large, medium or small what so ever-in size or capital, all are required the finance. Majority of the firms are raising capital from external sources. All are comes under the canvas of corporate finance. The study concludes that the four important goals pursued by Indian companies are ensuring the availability of funds, maximizing growth, maximizing operating profits before interest and taxes, and maximizing the rate of return on investment. This study offers young entrepreneurs, economists, and researchers a road map for obtaining corporate finance to starting a business venture in India and advocate the points of Future Research.

Keywords: G3 Corporate Finance, G11 Investment Decisions, G21 Bank, G23 Non-bank Financial Institutions

INTRODUCTION:

Developing countries like India need industries to grow their economy. India has a lot of people and resources, so industrialisation is important for its development. The most important thing about industrialization is that it helps the country make more money quickly. This is because more things are produce and people are earning more money individually. The second most important thing about industrialization is that it creates jobs and can make useful things out of limited resources. Many different things are made for less money and can sell at a lower price. It supports farming, protects the country, and helps the country grow evenly. Finance is one of the major tools that are required to setup an industry. It is Large, Medium or Small what so ever in size or capital, All are required the finance.

“Corporate finance refers to activities and transactions related to raising capital to create, develop and acquire a business.” It is directly related to company decisions that have a financial or monetary impact. The findings revealed that firm level factors such as firm size, dividend payout ratio and effective cost of borrowing, cash flow ratio and growth in value of production are significant in determining corporate finance decisions. The main areas of corporate finance are capital budgeting (for investing in company projects), capital financing (deciding how to fund projects/operations) and working capital management (managing assets and liabilities to operate efficiently).

Majority of the firms are raising the capital from external sources to meet their funding requirements. These include bank credit, equity markets, corporate bond markets, external commercial borrowings and private equity etc. While the banks have been slow in corporate lending, recently the equity and debt markets provide immense opportunities to corporate to raise cost-effective and long term capital. The primary market segment is witnessing flurry of activities with a number of IPOs lined up. Both BSE and NSE are expecting a surge in IPOs indicating a strong revival of the primary market. Further, it has observed that increasing number of corporate is utilizing the debt market to fund their borrowing needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Modigliani and Miller (1958), Myers and Majluf (1984), Fazzari (1988), Kaplan and Zingales (1997), Cleary (2007) were worked in the field of corporate finance. In the Indian context, Rajakumar (2005) verified empirically the relationship between corporate financing and investment behaviour for the period 1988-89 to 1998-99. However, Ramesh Jangili and Sharad Kumar published a research paper on the Determinants of Private Corporate Sector Investment in India for the period 2001-2008. Corporate Finance Practices in India: A Survey by Manoj Anand (2002) also throws the lime light in the same topic.

OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH:

- * Find out about the scope and challenges of corporate finance in India, as well as their solutions.
- * Discover the various emerging trends in corporate financing in India.
- * How do corporate investment decisions in India differ on a small, medium, and large scale?
- * How can entrepreneurs solve their financial requirements for their start-ups?

THE PROBLEM:

India is still a developing country where institutional financing is hard to find. In the current scenario, India has emerged as a startup hotspot with more than 80,000 startups in 2022. Every year, a large number of young people decide to become entrepreneurs. They are primarily using their savings to start their business. Most of the time, they will be fail. In the Indian context, there are certain issues with corporate financing. These are too much debt, excessive spending and limited marketing capital, boot strapping, ignoring budgets, and facing unexpected expenses. The majority of young entrepreneurs in India are unaware of the most recent trends in corporate finance. Without the collective study, it is hard to find a specific solution for young entrepreneurs that will boost their corporate finance decision-making in India.

METHOD:

I am conducting my research by adopting an empirical and iterative approach. Primarily, a preparation phase will involve a study through literature of the history and evolution of the corporate finance. In the secondary phase will look up the different publications, research journals, surveys and questionnaires. Summarize all the things to develop the final findings in last & final phase.

Here I am using the Secondary Research method.

“Secondary research is research that has already been compiled, gathered, organized and published by others”. Such data could be obtained faster and is more affordable. Secondary data is available through websites, reading articles, magazines, trade journals etc.

DISCUSSION:

There are many source of finance is found in the past scenario. Traditional Business Firms uses the following sources to raise the capital for their operation and expand. Some are

- * **Bank credit** - Bank credit is the amount of credit available to a business or individual from a banking institution in the form of loans. Bank credit, therefore, is the total amount of money a person or business can borrow from a bank or other financial institution.
- * **Equity markets** - An *equity market* is a market in which shares of companies are issued and traded, either through exchanges or through over-the-counter markets.
- * **Corporate bond markets** – After government bonds, the corporate bond market is the largest section of the global bond universe. With a vast array of maturities, yields and credit quality available, investing in corporate bonds has the potential to provide higher yields than government bonds and diversification benefits for investors.
- * **External commercial borrowings** - External Commercial Borrowing (ECB) is an instrument used to facilitate Indian companies or big corporations to raise money outside the country in foreign currency. External Commercial Borrowing is fundamentally a loan availed by an Indian company from a non-resident foreign-lender.
- * **Private equity** - In the field of finance, private equity (PE) is stock in a private company that does not offer stock to the general public. Private equity is offered instead to specialized investment funds and limited partnerships that take an active role in the management and structuring of the companies.

CHALLENGES:

Despite the growth and development of corporate finance in India, several challenges persist. These challenges can hinder the ability of companies to optimize their financial strategies and achieve sustainable growth.

- * **Regulatory Hurdles:** The Indian regulatory environment, though improving, remains complex and sometimes unpredictable. Companies often face challenges in navigating the myriad of regulations related to capital markets, taxation, and corporate governance. While reforms like the IBC and GST have been positive, the frequent changes in regulations can create uncertainty for businesses.
- * **Access to Capital:** While large corporations have relatively easier access to capital, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) often struggle to secure financing. The high cost of capital, coupled with stringent lending norms, makes it difficult for SMEs to raise funds, thereby limiting their growth potential. Additionally, the Indian financial system’s reliance on traditional banking channels poses a challenge for companies seeking alternative financing options.
- * **Corporate Governance:** Corporate governance remains a critical issue in India. Despite efforts to improve transparency and accountability, instances of corporate fraud and mismanagement continue to surface. Weak governance practices can undermine investor confidence and adversely affect a company’s

ability to raise capital. The need for stronger enforcement of corporate governance norms is paramount to ensuring the long-term sustainability of businesses.

* **Market Volatility:** The Indian financial markets are prone to volatility, driven by both domestic and global factors. Market fluctuations can have a significant impact on corporate finance activities, particularly in areas like capital raising and M&A. Companies need to develop robust strategies to manage the risks associated with market volatility, including diversification and hedging.

* **Technological Disruption:** While technology has brought numerous benefits to corporate finance, it has also introduced new challenges. The rapid pace of technological change can make it difficult for companies to keep up, particularly in areas like financial reporting, compliance, and risk management. Cyber security threats are another major concern, as financial data increasingly digitalized.

* **Too much debt** – Holding too much debt can cause financial hardship in several ways. Excessive debt is a significant challenge for corporate finance in India. Many Indian companies have historically relied on debt as a primary means of financing their growth and expansion, often leading to over-leveraging. This reliance on debt can strain a company's financial health, particularly during economic downturns or periods of high interest rates.

* **Excessive Spending** – Compulsive spending, sometimes-called compulsive buying disorder or Oniomania, is spending far beyond what is necessary. Though it often causes financial harm, people of means may engage in compulsive spending without suffering serious financial disaster.

* **Limited Market Capital** – Limited market capital is a notable challenge for corporate finance in India, particularly affecting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and new ventures. Unlike large corporations, which have relatively easier access to capital markets, SMEs often struggle to secure the necessary funding to grow and scale their operations.

* **Ignoring Budgets** - Ignoring a budget will remove the budgets impact from the cash flow. When removing a budget, this can be done on a budget occurrence level or budget as a whole level. To ignore a single budget occurrence, first click into the cell where the budget exists and then click into the budget itself.

New Trends of Corporate Finance in India

Due to Technological development, Corporate Finance in India is also experiencing the transformation. Some are

Fig. 1

Digital Transformation - As traditional business models are transforming and companies are looking for new ways to be more agile, the focus of corporate finance professionals is shifting toward digital transformation. This trend has been driven by the need for a more effective and efficient business model. Companies are now looking at e-commerce as a way to increase customer engagement and sales. In addition, they are also looking at online marketing as an effective way to enhance brand image and awareness.

Integration of FinTech & Financial Institutions – The integration of FinTech & financial institutions is another emerging trend in corporate finance. This trend has been driven by the need for more efficient financing solutions for corporations. Corporates are looking at FinTech companies as a way to reduce costs and improve efficiency in terms of accessing funding options from various sources in one place.

IPO Finance for corporate - IPO is the public offering of a company's shares and a way for a company to raise capital by selling its shares to the public. The process begins when an entrepreneur or business plans on issuing new shares for sale at an initial public offering (IPO), which usually occurs after it has grown into a successful and profitable entity. When this happens, investors can buy these newly issued shares in order to gain ownership stakes in those companies.

FPOs (Follow on Public Offer) - FPOs are used to finance a company's growth. They can be used to bridge the gap between the company's existing debt and equity, and they allow additional capital to be raised without diluting ownership or control of your assets. FPOs typically have a longer maturity period than traditional debt instruments, so you're able to use them as long-term financing solutions for projects with low-risk profiles.

Merger & Acquisition - Mergers and acquisitions are a way for companies to grow. They can be used by organizations as a way to expand their businesses or by investors who want to buy into promising companies at an attractive price. Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A) are often viewed as positive steps in the life cycle of an organization because they contribute positively to long-term growth prospects and increase shareholder value.

Private Equity - Private equity is a form of investment in which the investor does not have any control over the management of the company. Private equity firms are large and dynamic entities that provide financial resources to help companies expand their operations or acquire other companies and franchises. They also offer management services to help their portfolio companies operate more efficiently through their expertise in finance, accounting, human resources, and general management.

Corporate bond market - The corporate bond market is a place where corporate can raise funds, borrow money, or invest in bonds. Bonds are debt securities that entitle the issuer (the borrower) to interest payments over time and repay the principal at maturity. Companies or governments around the world issue them in order to finance projects like infrastructure, equipment purchases, etc. They are typically not fixed-rate securities because their value depends on how much investor believe they will sell for at maturity.

ANALYSIS:

India, a developing nation with a vast population and abundant resources, is on a trajectory toward industrialization, which is critical for its economic growth. The industrial sector is pivotal in generating wealth, creating employment, and utilizing resources efficiently. Corporate finance, therefore, plays a crucial role in supporting the industrialization process by providing the necessary capital for business creation, development, and expansion. Now, India has emerged as a startup hotspot with more than 80,000 startups in 2022. . India has 108 unicorns during 2023 and will likely have more in the future. BYJU's, Swiggy, OYO Rooms, Dream11, Razorpay, and Ola Cabs are examples of India's Top Unicorn Companies. In India, a spiral effect is at work: as more unicorns were produced, more are born. Between 2015 and 2021, India's start-up ecosystem saw a nine-time increase in investment and a seven-time increase in funding.

A large number of youngsters are choosing entrepreneurship every year. Some start-ups become unicorn companies, but the majority fail within a few years. There are several factors responsible for the failure of a start-ups in which Finance plays a vital role. Due to a lack of information, the majority of young entrepreneurs choose the wrong path in corporate finance. Without a collective study, it is hard to find a specific solution so the topic requires an intensive research.

OUTCOMES:

The comprehensive analysis of corporate finance in India highlights several key outcomes that are vital for understanding the current landscape, challenges, and emerging trends. These outcomes provide insights that can inform both policy and business strategies, contributing to more effective decision-making in the field of corporate finance.

1. Expanding Scope of Corporate Finance

The analysis reveals that the scope of corporate finance in India is broadening, driven by the country's economic growth and the increasing complexity of financial markets. The diversification of capital sources, including equity markets, corporate bonds, and external commercial borrowings, has provided Indian companies with a wider array of financing options. This expansion is particularly beneficial for large corporations that have the resources to tap into multiple funding channels, thereby optimizing their capital structure.

2. Persistent Challenges for SMEs

Despite the growth of corporate finance, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in India continue to face significant challenges in accessing capital. The analysis underscores that SMEs often struggle with high costs of capital, limited access to equity markets, and stringent lending norms. These challenges hinder the growth potential of SMEs, which are critical to India's economic development. Addressing these issues is essential for fostering a more inclusive financial ecosystem that supports businesses of all sizes.

3. Regulatory and Governance Issues

The analysis identifies regulatory hurdles and corporate governance as ongoing challenges in the Indian corporate finance landscape. While recent reforms like the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC) and Goods and Services Tax (GST) have had positive impacts, the regulatory environment remains complex and sometimes unpredictable. Additionally, weak corporate governance practices continue to pose risks, undermining investor confidence and affecting companies' ability to raise capital. Strengthening regulatory frameworks and enforcing governance standards are crucial for ensuring the sustainability of the corporate sector.

4. Market Volatility and Financial Risk Management

Market volatility, driven by both domestic and global factors is highlighted as a significant concern for corporate finance in India. The analysis shows that fluctuations in financial markets can disrupt corporate finance activities, particularly in capital raising and mergers and acquisitions (M&A). This underscores the need for Indian companies to develop robust financial risk management strategies, including diversification and hedging, to mitigate the impact of market volatility.

5. Technological Disruption and Digital Transformation

The emergence of digital technologies is transforming the corporate finance landscape in India. The analysis points to digital transformation as a major trend, with companies increasingly adopting technology to enhance financial processes, improve efficiency, and reduce costs. However, the rapid pace of technological change also presents challenges, particularly in areas like cyber security and financial reporting. Companies need to invest in technology while simultaneously managing the risks associated with digital disruption.

6. Opportunities in Sustainable and Inclusive Finance

The analysis suggests that there are growing opportunities in sustainable finance, driven by the global emphasis on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors. Indian companies are beginning to recognize the importance of integrating ESG considerations into their financial strategies. Additionally, there is a push towards more inclusive finance, with efforts to improve access to capital for underrepresented segments of the economy, such as SMEs and startups. These trends are expected to shape the future of corporate finance in India, aligning it with global best practices.

7. Strategic Implications for Entrepreneurs and Start-ups

For entrepreneurs and startups, the analysis reveals that understanding the nuances of corporate finance is critical for success. Many young entrepreneurs in India face challenges related to limited financial literacy, leading to poor financial decision-making and business failures. The outcomes highlight the need for targeted education and support programs that equip entrepreneurs with the knowledge and tools to navigate the complexities of corporate finance. This is particularly important in a startup ecosystem that is rapidly expanding but also highly competitive.

8. Policy Recommendations for Enhancing Corporate Finance

Based on the analysis, several policy recommendations can be made to enhance the corporate finance environment in India. These include:

- **Simplifying Regulatory Processes:** Streamlining regulatory procedures and reducing bureaucratic hurdles can make it easier for businesses to raise capital and operate efficiently.
- **Improving Access to Capital for SMEs:** Developing financial instruments and platforms that cater specifically to the needs of SMEs can help bridge the funding gap for smaller businesses.
- **Promoting Financial Literacy:** Initiatives to improve financial literacy among entrepreneurs and business leaders can lead to better financial decision-making and business outcomes.
- **Encouraging Sustainable Finance:** Incentivizing companies to adopt sustainable finance practices can contribute to long-term economic and environmental benefits.

9. Future Research Directions

The outcomes of this analysis also suggest several points for future research. These include:

- **Exploring the Impact of Digital Transformation on Corporate Finance:** Further research is needed to understand the long-term effects of digital technologies on corporate finance, particularly in areas like financial management, compliance, and risk mitigation.
- **Assessing the Effectiveness of Regulatory Reforms:** Evaluating the impact of recent regulatory changes on corporate finance practices can provide valuable insights for policymakers and business leaders.
- **Investigating the Role of ESG in Corporate Finance:** As sustainable finance gains traction, there is a need for research that examines how the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors influence corporate finance decisions and outcomes in India.

CONCLUSION:

Corporate finance is constantly evolving, and it can be difficult to keep up with the latest trends. However, understanding these emerging trends in corporate finance can help businesses make better decisions that will lead to improved financial health and increased long-term success. From leveraging technology for efficiency gains to using big data analytics for decision-making, companies must stay ahead of the curve if they want to remain viable and competitive in this ever-changing landscape. In Indian context, corporate finance is at a pivotal juncture, with significant opportunities and challenges ahead. The scope of corporate finance is expanding, driven by economic growth, market development, and technological advancements. However, challenges such as regulatory hurdles, access to capital, and market volatility persist. Emerging trends like digital transformation, sustainable finance, and globalization are set to reshape the corporate finance landscape in India. As India continues its journey towards becoming a global economic powerhouse, the role of corporate finance will be crucial in driving sustainable growth and enhancing the competitiveness of Indian businesses. Stakeholders, including policymakers, businesses, and financial institutions, must work together to address the challenges and leverage the opportunities presented by the evolving corporate finance landscape.

REFERENCES:

Journal Papers:

- * Emerging Trends in Corporate Finance in India (2015)
- by *Resurgent India*, Confederation of Indian Industries
- * Determinants of Private Corporate Sector Investment in India (2010)
- by Ramesh Jangili and Sharad Kumar (*Reserve Bank of India Occasional Papers* Vol. 31, No. 3, Winter 2010)
- * Corporate Financing and Investment Behaviors in India (2005)
-by Rajakumar, J Dennis (*Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. 40, No. 38, September 17-23, pp.4159-4165)
- * The Relationship between Firm Investment and Financial Status (1999)

-by Cleary, S (*The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 54, No. 2, Apr 1999, pp.673-692)

* Corporate Financing and Investment Decisions when Firms Have Information Investors do not have
- by Myers, S. and Majluf, N. (1984) (*Journal of Financial Economics*, 13, pp.187-221.)

* The Cost of Capital, Corporate Finance, and the Theory of Investment (1958)
- by Modigliani, F. and Miller (*American Economic Review*, 48, pp.261-297)